

ENGLISH-UZBEK EDUCATIONAL TERMINOLOGY ON HIGH
EDUCATION

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Abstract: as we know, education is being a widespread factor to build strong relationship between countries. In this case, it is required to grasp educational terminology deeply to aware of the education system of other nationalities.

Key words: education, grade, college, refer, attend, years, qualifications, difference

Educational terminology can differ between countries, including between English-speaking countries. Here are some specific differences in educational terminology between the United States and the United Kingdom as examples:

- In the United States, students are typically referred to by their grade level (e.g., 1st grade, 8th grade, 12th grade).

- In the United Kingdom, students are referred to by their year group (e.g., Year 1, Year 8, Year 12).

- In the United States, "college" often refers to institutions that offer undergraduate degrees, while "university" typically refers to institutions that offer both undergraduate and graduate programs.

- In the United Kingdom, "college" generally refers to post-secondary institutions that offer a variety of courses, while "university" refers to institutions that grant degrees, including both undergraduate and postgraduate programs.

- In the United States, students attend "high school" from grades 9 to 12.

- In the United Kingdom, students attend "secondary school" from Year 7 to Year 11 or Year 12, depending on the education system.

- In the United States, a "thesis" is typically associated with a master's degree, while a "dissertation" is associated with a doctoral degree.

- In the United Kingdom, the terms "dissertation" and "thesis" are often used interchangeably, but they may vary depending on the institution and the specific degree.

- In the United States, an "associate degree" is a two-year undergraduate degree.

- In the United Kingdom, a "foundation degree" is a higher education qualification that typically takes two years to complete and is designed to provide students with the skills and knowledge necessary for employment or further study.

- In the United Kingdom, undergraduate degrees often come in two forms: "ordinary" and "honors." An honors degree typically indicates a higher level of academic achievement and may require a research project or dissertation. In the United States, there is no equivalent terminology for this distinction.

- In the United Kingdom, students take General Certificate of Secondary Education (GCSE) exams typically at the end of Year 11.

- In the United States, students may take the SAT or ACT exams as part of the college admissions process.

These are just a few examples of how educational terminology can differ between English-speaking countries. It's important to be aware of these differences when discussing education across borders, as terms may have different meanings or connotations in different contexts.

Terminology in higher education can vary from one language to another, and it's important to have a clear understanding of key terms when working in an English-speaking academic environment. Here are some English-Uzbek terminology pairs commonly used in higher education:

These are some common terms used in higher education, but the terminology may vary depending on the specific academic institution or context in Uzbekistan. It's essential to be familiar with these terms to navigate the academic environment effectively.

Uzbek educational terminology follows a set of specific rules and conventions

that are influenced by the Uzbek language and educational system. Here are some specific rules and considerations regarding Uzbek educational terminology:

Uzbekistan primarily uses the Cyrillic script for writing the Uzbek language. Therefore, educational terminology in Uzbek is often written in Cyrillic characters. However, there have been efforts to transition to the Latin script.

Uzbekistan has established official terminology for higher education, and it's important to use these standardized terms in academic and administrative contexts. The government and educational institutions may publish guidelines for terminology usage.

Due to historical ties to the Soviet Union, some educational terms in Uzbek may have been borrowed from Russian. For example, "бакалавр" (bakalavr) for "bachelor" and "магистр" (magistr) for "master" are borrowed from Russian.

Uzbek educational terminology closely follows the Russian system for degree designations. For example:

- Bakalavr (Бакалавр): Equivalent to a bachelor's degree.
- Magistr (Магистр): Equivalent to a master's degree.
- Doktorantura (Докторантура): Equivalent to a doctorate/Ph.D. program.

Uzbek, like many Turkic languages, has gender agreement in nouns and adjectives. Some educational terms may change based on gender. For instance, "professor" is "профессор" (professor) for a male professor and "профессора" (professora) for a female professor.

In Uzbek, pluralization is achieved by modifying the noun. Plural forms may differ from the singular forms, so it's important to use the correct form when referring to multiple items or individuals.

When transitioning to the Latin script, there may be variations in transliteration. For example, "университет" (universitet) in Cyrillic script can be transliterated as "universitet" or "universitet" depending on the adopted transliteration system.

Academic titles like "professor" (профессор) and "lecturer" (лектор) may have specific requirements and criteria for their use, similar to other countries.

While there are standardized terms, it's essential to be aware that variations and regional differences in terminology may exist within Uzbekistan, particularly in dialects and informal settings.

Uzbekistan has undergone educational reforms in recent years, including language and script reforms. It's important to stay updated on any changes in educational terminology as the country's language and educational systems evolve.

To ensure accuracy and clarity when using Uzbek educational terminology, it's advisable to refer to official sources, guidelines provided by educational institutions, and language authorities in Uzbekistan. Additionally, consider the context in which the terminology is used, as some terms may have specific meanings in higher education.

Reference

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